

A APPENDIX: Task Code for Type Inference Experiment

```
1 public class Task1 {
2     /*
3     Your task is to initialize and start the game.
4     Therefore, you need to generate a default level,
5     add some information about the level and
6     finally start the game.
7     */
8
9     public static void initializeAndStartGame (MethodParameters
10         ↪ methodParameters) {
11         Game mainModel = methodParameters.mainModel;
12         Window frame = methodParameters.frame;
13         LevelGeneratorFactory = methodParameters.factory;
14         PlayerHero = methodParameters.hero;
15
16         // Solution starts here
17         Level level = factory.generateDefaultLevel();
18         Difficulty d = factory.calculateDifficulty( level.getMonsters());
19         mainModel.computeStars (hero, d);
20         Achievement a = factory.constructReward( level.getPlatforms(), hero);
21         mainModel.prefetchBadges(a) ;
22         mainModel.updateGameInfo(level, hero);
23         frame.getPanel().startGame( mainModel, level.getPreview().toJPEG());
24     }
25 }
```

Figure 8: Method template (line 1-16) and possible solution for programming task 1 with type annotations

```

1 public class Task2 {
2     /*
3     Your task is to make the game more difficult.
4     Therefore you need to extend the level with some
5     barriers, add a boss monster and finally process
6     the level update.
7     */
8
9     public static void makeGameMoreDifficult (MethodParams encapsulationObject
10         ↪ ) {
11         def barriers = encapsulationObject.barriers;
12         def currentScore = encapsulationObject.score;
13         def gameLevel = encapsulationObject.gameLevel;
14         def mainModel = encapsulationObject.mainModel;
15
16         // Solution starts here
17         def extParams = barriers.convertForLevelExtension();
18         def d = currentScore.getDifficulty();
19         def le = gameLevel.extentLevel(extParams, d);
20         def progress = currentScore.getProgress();
21         def boss = mainModel.getAppropriateBossForProgress(progress);
22         le.addFinalEnemy (boss) ;
23         def additionalScoringStrategy = mainModel.createBonusScoring(
24             ↪ currentScore);
25         le.setAdditionalScoring(additionalScoringStrategy);
26         mainModel.processLevelUpdate(le);
27     }
28 }

```

Figure 9: Method template (line 1-14) and possible solution for programming task 2 with type inference

B APPENDIX: Task Code for Enumerated Type Experiment

```
1 package code;
2 public class CellNetwork {
3
4     /**
5     * TODO: Based on the code samples you saw, create the following
6     * items in your class.
7     *
8     * ATNT
9     * VERIZON
10    * SPRINT
11    * TMOBILE
12    * USCELLULAR
13    */
14    // First part of Solution
15    public enum Network
16    {
17        ATNT, VERIZON, SPRINT, TMOBILE, USCELLULAR
18    }
19    // end first part of solution
20
21    /**
22    * TODO: Complete the method below.
23    * -----
24    * Here are the names for your network.
25    * -ATNT is "AT&T"
26    * -VERIZON is "Verizon Wireless"
27    * -SPRINT is "Sprint Corporation"
28    * -TMOBILE is "T-Mobile"
29    * -USCELLULAR is "U.S. Cellular"
30    *
31    */
32    public String getNetworkCompanyName(Network network) {
33
34        String networkName = "";
35        // Second part of the solution
36        if (network == Network.ATNT) {
37            networkName = "AT&T";
38        } else if (network == Network.VERIZON) {
39            networkName = "Verizon Wireless";
40        } else if (network == Network.SPRINT) {
41            networkName = "Sprint Corporation";
42        } else if (network == Network.TMOBILE) {
43            networkName = "T-Mobile";
44        } else if (network == Network.USCELLULAR) {
45            networkName = "U.S. Cellular";
46        } else {
47            networkName = "UNKNOWN";
48        }
49        // end second part of solution
50
51        return networkName;
52    }
53 }
```

Figure 10: Enum group task 1 with solution marked with comments.

```

1 package code;
2 public class CellNetwork {
3
4     /**
5     * TODO: Based on the code samples you saw, create the following
6     * items in your class.
7     *
8     * ATNT
9     * VERIZON
10    * SPRINT
11    * TMOBILE
12    * USCELLULAR
13    */
14    // First part of Solution
15    public static final int ATNT = 0;
16    public static final int VERIZON = 1;
17    public static final int SPRINT = 2;
18    public static final int TMOBILE = 3;
19    public static final int USCELLULAR = 4;
20    // end first part of solution
21
22    /**
23    * TODO: Complete the method below.
24    * -----
25    * Here are the names for your network.
26    * -ATNT is "AT&T"
27    * -VERIZON is "Verizon Wireless"
28    * -SPRINT is "Sprint Corporation"
29    * -TMOBILE is "T-Mobile"
30    * -USCELLULAR is "U.S. Cellular"
31    *
32    */
33    public String getNetworkCompanyName(int network) {
34        String provider = "";
35
36        // Second part of the solution
37        if (network == ATNT) {
38            provider = "AT&T";
39        } else if (network == VERIZON) {
40            provider = "Verizon Wireless";
41        } else if (network == SPRINT) {
42            provider = "Sprint Corporation";
43        } else if (network == TMOBILE) {
44            provider = "T-Mobile";
45        } else if (network == USCELLULAR) {
46            provider = "U.S. Cellular";
47        }
48        // end second part of solution
49
50        return provider;
51    }
52 }

```

Figure 11: Constant group task 1 with solution marked with comments.

```

1 package code;
2 import java.util.ArrayList;
3 import java.util.List;
4
5 public class WebServer {
6     List webpages;
7     public WebServer() {
8         initialize();
9     }
10    private void initialize() {
11        this.webpages = new ArrayList();
12        this.webpages.add("google.com");
13        this.webpages.add("stackoverflow.com");
14        this.webpages.add("dzone.com");
15    }
16    /**
17     * TODO: Based on the samples you saw, create the following items of type
18     *       ↪ HTTPErrorCodes.
19     * OK, code: 200, name: "OK", description: "Action completed successfully."
20     * CREATED, code: 201, name: "Created", description: "Success following a
21     *       ↪ post command."
22     * NO_CONTENT, code: 204, name: "No Content", description: "Server has
23     *       ↪ received the request but there is no content to send back."
24     * MOVED_PERMANENTLY, code: 301, name: "Moved Permanently", description: "
25     *       ↪ Requested a directory instead of a specific file. The web server
26     *       ↪ added the filename index.html, index.htm, home.html, or home.htm to
27     *       ↪ the URL."
28     * BAD_REQUEST, code: 400, name: "Bad Request", description: "The request
29     *       ↪ had bad syntax or was impossible to be satisfied."
30     * UNAUTHORIZED, code: 401, name: "Unauthorized", description: "User failed
31     *       ↪ to provide a valid user name / password required for access to file
32     *       ↪ / directory."
33     * FORBIDDEN, code: 403, name: "Forbidden", description: "The request does
34     *       ↪ not specify the file name. Or the directory or the file does not
35     *       ↪ have the permission that allows the pages to be viewed from the web
36     *       ↪ ."
37     * NOT_FOUND, code: 404, name: "Not Found", description: "The requested file
38     *       ↪ was not found."
39     * SERVER_ERROR, code: 500, name: "Server Error", description: "In most
40     *       ↪ cases, this error is a result of a problem with the code or program
41     *       ↪ you are calling rather than with the web server itself."
42     * NOT_IMPLEMENTED, code: 501, name: "Not Implemented", description: "The
43     *       ↪ server does not support the facility required."
44     * SERVICE_UNAVAILABLE, code: 503, name: "Service Unavailable", description:
45     *       ↪ "The server cannot process the request due to a system overload.
46     *       ↪ This should be a temporary condition."
47     * GATEWAY_TIMEOUT, code: 504, name: "Gateway Timeout", description: "The
48     *       ↪ service did not respond within the time frame that the gateway was
49     *       ↪ willing to wait." *
50     * Override toString() method of the type to return a string that is ::
51     * Example:
52     * 200:OK:Action completed successfully
53     */
54    public static class HTTPErrorCodes {
55        \\ Your Code Here
56    }
57    \\ Your Code Here
58 }

```

Figure 12: Constant group task 2.

```

1 public static class HTTPErrorCodes {
2     public int codeNum;
3     public String errName;
4     public String errDesc;
5     public HTTPErrorCodes(int num, String name, String desc) {
6         this.codeNum = num;
7         this.errName = name;
8         this.errDesc = desc;
9     }
10    @Override
11    public String toString () {
12        return codeNum + ":" + errName + ":" + errDesc;
13    }
14 }
15 public static final HTTPErrorCodes OK = new HTTPErrorCodes (200, "OK", "
16     ↪ Action completed successfully.");
17 public static final HTTPErrorCodes CREATED = new HTTPErrorCodes (201, "
18     ↪ Created", "Success following a post command.");
19 public static final HTTPErrorCodes NO_CONTENT = new HTTPErrorCodes (204, "
20     ↪ No Content", "Server has received the request but there is no
21     ↪ content to send back.");
22 public static final HTTPErrorCodes MOVED_PERMANENTLY = new HTTPErrorCodes
23     ↪ (301, "Moved Permanently", "Requested a directory instead of a
24     ↪ specific file. The web server added the filename index.html, index.
25     ↪ htm, home.html, or home.htm to the URL.");
26 public static final HTTPErrorCodes BAD_REQUEST = new HTTPErrorCodes (400, "
27     ↪ Bad Request", "The request had bad syntax or was impossible to be
28     ↪ satisfied.");
29 public static final HTTPErrorCodes UNAUTHORIZED = new HTTPErrorCodes (401,
30     ↪ "Unauthorized", "User failed to provide a valid user name /
31     ↪ password required for access to file / directory.");
32 public static final HTTPErrorCodes FORBIDDEN = new HTTPErrorCodes (403, "
33     ↪ Forbidden", "The request does not specify the file name. Or the
34     ↪ directory or the file does not have the permission that allows the
35     ↪ pages to be viewed from the web.");
36 public static final HTTPErrorCodes NOT_FOUND = new HTTPErrorCodes (404, "
37     ↪ Not Found", "The requested file was not found.");
38 public static final HTTPErrorCodes SERVER_ERROR = new HTTPErrorCodes (500,
39     ↪ "Server Error", "In most cases, this error is a result of a problem
40     ↪ with the code or program you are calling rather than with the web
41     ↪ server itself.");
42 public static final HTTPErrorCodes NOT_IMPLEMENTED = new HTTPErrorCodes
43     ↪ (501, "Not Implemented", "The server does not support the facility
44     ↪ required.");
45 public static final HTTPErrorCodes SERVICE_UNAVAILABLE = new HTTPErrorCodes
46     ↪ (503, "Service Unavailable", "The server cannot process the
47     ↪ request due to a system overload. This should be a temporary
48     ↪ condition.");
49 public static final HTTPErrorCodes GATEWAY_TIMEOUT = new HTTPErrorCodes
50     ↪ (504, "Gateway Timeout", "The service did not respond within the
51     ↪ time frame that the gateway was willing to wait.");

```

Figure 13: Constant group task 2 solution.

```

1 package code;
2 import java.util.ArrayList;
3 import java.util.List;
4
5 public class WebServer {
6     List webpages;
7     public WebServer() {
8         initialize();
9     }
10    private void initialize() {
11        this.webpages = new ArrayList();
12        this.webpages.add("google.com");
13        this.webpages.add("stackoverflow.com");
14        this.webpages.add("dzone.com");
15    }
16    /**
17     * TODO: Based on the samples you saw, create the following items of type
18     * ↪ HTTPErrorCodes.
19     *
20     * OK, code: 200, name: "OK", description: "Action completed successfully."
21     * CREATED, code: 201, name: "Created", description: "Success following a
22     * ↪ post command."
23     * NO_CONTENT, code: 204, name: "No Content", description: "Server has
24     * ↪ received the request but there is no content to send back."
25     * MOVED_PERMANENTLY, code: 301, name: "Moved Permanently", description: "
26     * ↪ Requested a directory instead of a specific file. The web server
27     * ↪ added the filename index.html, index.htm, home.html, or home.htm to
28     * ↪ the URL."
29     * BAD_REQUEST, code: 400, name: "Bad Request", description: "The request
30     * ↪ had bad syntax or was impossible to be satisfied."
31     * UNAUTHORIZED, code: 401, name: "Unauthorized", description: "User failed
32     * ↪ to provide a valid user name / password required for access to file
33     * ↪ / directory."
34     * FORBIDDEN, code: 403, name: "Forbidden", description: "The request does
35     * ↪ not specify the file name. Or the directory or the file does not
36     * ↪ have the permission that allows the pages to be viewed from the web
37     * ↪ ."
38     * NOT_FOUND, code: 404, name: "Not Found", description: "The requested file
39     * ↪ was not found."
40     * SERVER_ERROR, code: 500, name: "Server Error", description: "In most
41     * ↪ cases, this error is a result of a problem with the code or program
42     * ↪ you are calling rather than with the web server itself."
43     * NOT_IMPLEMENTED, code: 501, name: "Not Implemented", description: "The
44     * ↪ server does not support the facility required."
45     * SERVICE_UNAVAILABLE, code: 503, name: "Service Unavailable", description:
46     * ↪ "The server cannot process the request due to a system overload.
47     * ↪ This should be a temporary condition."
48     * GATEWAY_TIMEOUT, code: 504, name: "Gateway Timeout", description: "The
49     * ↪ service did not respond within the time frame that the gateway was
50     * ↪ willing to wait." *
51     * Override toString() method of the type to return a string that is ::
52     * Example:
53     * 200:OK:Action completed successfully
54     *
55     */
56    public enum HTTPErrorCodes {
57        \\ Your Code Here
58    }
59 }

```

Figure 14: Enum group task 2.

```

1 public enum HTTPErrorCodes {
2     OK( 200, "OK", "Action completed successfully."),
3     CREATED( 201, "Created", "Success following a post command."),
4     NO_CONTENT( 204, "No Content", "Server has received the request but there
        ↳ is no content to send back."),
5     MOVED_PERMANENTLY( 301, "Moved Permanently", "Requested a directory
        ↳ instead of a specific file. The web server added the filename
        ↳ index.html, index.htm, home.html, or home.htm to the URL."),
6     BAD_REQUEST( 400, "Bad Request", "The request had bad syntax or was
        ↳ impossible to be satisfied."),
7     UNAUTHORIZED( 401, "Unauthorized", "User failed to provide a valid user
        ↳ name/ password required for access to file/ directory."),
8     FORBIDDEN( 403, "Forbidden", "The request does not specify the file name.
        ↳ Or the directory or the file does not have the permission that
        ↳ allows the pages to be viewed from the web."),
9     NOT_FOUND( 404, "Not Found", "The requested file was not found."),
10    SERVER_ERROR( 500, "Server Error", "In most cases, this error is a result
        ↳ of a problem with the code or program you are calling rather
        ↳ than with the web server itself."),
11    NOT_IMPLEMENTED( 501, "Not Implemented", "The server does not support the
        ↳ facility required."),
12    SERVICE_UNAVAILABLE( 503, "Service Unavailable", "The server cannot
        ↳ process the request due to a system overload. This should be a
        ↳ temporary condition."),
13    GATEWAY_TIMEOUT( 504, "Gateway Timeout", "The service did not respond
        ↳ within the time frame that the gateway was willing to wait.");
14    int code;
15    String name;
16    String description;
17    private HTTPErrorCodes(int code, String name, String desc) {
18        this.code = code;
19        this.name = name;
20        this.description = desc;
21    }
22    @Override
23    public String toString() {
24        return code + ":" + name + ":" + description;
25    }
26 }

```

Figure 15: Enum group task 2 solution.

```

1 package samples;
2 public class Sample4 {
3
4     /*
5      * Similar kind of declaration might be useful for the tasks.
6      */
7     public enum Day {
8
9         SUNDAY( 1, "Sunday", "a_relaxing_day"),
10        MONDAY( 2, "Monday", "a_boring_day"),
11        TUESDAY( 3, "Tuesday", "just_a_day"),
12        WEDNESDAY( 4, "Wednesday", "a_mid-week_crisis_day"),
13        THURSDAY( 5, "Thursday", "almost_there_to_fun_times"),
14        FRIDAY( 6, "Friday", "a_TGIF"),
15        SATURDAY( 7, "Saturday", "a_Weekend");
16
17        int dayOfWeek;
18        String dayName;
19        String description;
20
21        private Day(int dayOfWeek, String name, String desc) {
22            this.dayOfWeek = dayOfWeek;
23            this.dayName = name;
24            this.description= desc;
25        }
26
27        @Override
28        public String toString() {
29            return "dayOfWeek=" + dayOfWeek + " name=" + dayName + "
30                ↪ description=" + description;
31        }
32    }
33    public static void main(String[] args) {
34        for (int i = 0; i < Day.values().length; i++) {
35            Day day = Day.values()[i];
36            System.out.println(day.dayName + " is day " + day.dayOfWeek + " and "
37                ↪ + day.description );
38        }
39    }
40 }

```

Figure 16: One of the samples for the Enum group

```

1 package samples;
2 public class Sample2 {
3
4     public static final int OFF = 0;
5     public static final int ON = 1;
6
7     /*
8      * Similar type of switch usage might be useful for the tasks.
9      */
10    public String turnSwitch(int action) {
11
12        String result = "";
13        if (action == ON) {
14            result = "Switch turned on";
15        } else if (action == OFF) {
16            result = "Switch turned off";
17        }
18        return result;
19    }
20
21    public static void main(String[] args) {
22        Sample2 obj = new Sample2();
23        System.out.println(obj.turnSwitch(Sample2.OFF));
24        System.out.println(obj.turnSwitch(Sample2.ON));
25    }
26 }

```

Figure 17: One of the samples for the constants group